

ADVANCED SYSTEM FOR THE INTERACTIVE
ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF GEOPHYSICAL DATA

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Abstract

The Program for Regional Observing and Forecasting Services (PROFS) has developed a highly flexible, interactive system for improved weather forecasting. Several real-time tests with the participation of operational forecasters have demonstrated the viability of the system. The modular, systematic approach employed in developing the PROFS system makes it possible to apply the PROFS processing and display techniques in other areas as well.

1. Introduction

The Program for Regional Observing and Forecasting Services (PROFS) was established in 1979 to improve short-range, operational weather services. PROFS' mission includes the development and testing of new research and technological advances and the transfer of proven techniques to operational use. The first few years were devoted mainly to the development of the necessary computer facility and associated software. Presently, PROFS' emphasis is shifting toward the use of the facility to develop, test, and evaluate new forecasting techniques and transfer them to operations.

2. The PROFS System

The PROFS Exploratory Development Facility (EDF) was developed as a test bed to assess and evaluate new forecasting techniques. The EDF is a network of 14 mini and mid-sized computers configured to acquire and store a large variety of meteorological data, analyze and process the data into products, and display the products in an interactive workstation environment (Brown, 1983). A simplified diagram of the EDF is shown in Figure 1.

Each of the eleven data-source interfaces is a 16-bit Digital Equipment Corporation (DEC) PDP-11/24, or PDP-11/23 minicomputer. These front-end machines handle the communications protocols for the various data sources, perform error checking, and preprocess and calibrate the data, as appropriate. Conventional meteorological radar reflectivity data are acquired every five minutes from National Weather Service (NWS) radars located in Limon, Colorado and Cheyenne, Wyoming. Doppler radar reflectivity and velocity

Figure 1. The PROFS computer network.

data are obtained from the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) CP-2 research radar. A satellite ground station developed in cooperation with NCAR provides half-hourly Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) visible and infrared images. Acquisition of hourly Surface Aviation Observations (SAOs) and twice-daily upper-air soundings is accomplished through a passive, listen-only connection to the NWS Automation of Field Operations and Services (AFOS) network. The AFOS tap also provides PROFS with selected text messages and graphics products generated by the National Meteorological Center (NMC). Cloud-to-ground lightning strikes in the Colorado Front Range area are reported by a detection system operated jointly by the U. S. Air Force and PROFS. PROFS has developed a 22-station automated surface observing network (called mesonet) that covers part of the Colorado Front Range (Pratte and Clark, 1983). The mesonet provides five-minute averages of wind, temperature, dew-point temperature, pressure, and solar radiation, and five-minute totals of precipitation at each site. Vertical wind profiles are measured hourly at five sites in Colorado by high-frequency, Doppler radar devices developed by the Wave Propagation Laboratory (WPL) of ERL. At one site, Denver, passive radiometers also provide profiles of temperature and moisture every 20 minutes. Currently, PROFS is in the process of developing a connection to the new NMC Product Service via commercial satellite. The NMC link will provide Limited-area Fine-Mesh (LFM) model grid values.

All of the above data are transmitted from the local or remote data-source interfaces to the data acquisition/concentrator computer, PROFS1.

PROFS1 is a mid-sized, 32-bit DEC VAX-11/780 computer. PROFS1 creates the raw data files on a disk drive shared by PROFS1 and PROFS2, a second VAX-11/780. Approximately 150 megabytes (MB) of raw data are ingested and stored each day. PROFS does not have a conventional data-base management system. Files are organized by time and data source using DEC's file management system and accessed by PROFS-developed routines. The advantages of this approach are easy and efficient data access that is essential for a real-time system, isolation of users from the intricacies of the file formats, and protection of data integrity.

PROFS2 processes the data and generates the necessary meteorological products. PROFS2 performs a large variety of tasks all the way from remapping the satellite images to providing streamline analyses of wind fields. Products are generated on four scales: (1) National incorporating the continental U. S.; (2) Regional covering approximately a five-state area centered on Colorado; (3) Eastern Colorado including eastern two-thirds of Colorado, Southeastern Wyoming, and Southwestern Nebraska; and (4) Local encompassing a small portion of Northeastern Colorado. Over 100 products are created including 40 AFOS graphics products. A number of these products are generated on a five-minute cycle time. The volume of products stored on the disk shared by PROFS2 and PROFS3, a VAX-11/750, approaches 300 MB each day. Because of the large volume of data and products, they are purged after a suitable time period has expired, unless an interesting meteorological event warrants saving them off-line.

The workstation host, PROFS3, is capable of driving up to three independent workstations. The products created by PROFS2 are accessed by PROFS3 using the shared disk between the two computers. Each workstation has a Ramtek 9400 color video display system for displaying products. The great majority of products are displayed using 512x512 pixel resolution and 6 to 8 bits pixel depth. A Ramtek 6211 color video terminal is used for menu selection and command input. The forecaster requests a display of any single product, or a combination (overlay) of two or more products, by touching the 6211 menu/command screen. Additional workstation capabilities include zooming and roaming of the displays. Animation (looping) of up to 16 frames is also possible. Time-series plots of various meteorological variables (temperature, wind speed and direction, for example) and plots of derived fields from analyses are available as applications processes. Entering all the above commands through the touch screen has the advantage of eliminating the need for a keyboard and the necessity of direct forecaster interaction with the computer. Most forecasters learned to use the system within an hour.

The design philosophy in developing the PROFS distributed processing network was to emphasize both hardware and software modularity. For example, the failure of one of the data-

acquisition interfaces, such as Limon radar, does not affect the proper functioning of any of the other ingest interfaces. Modularity has resulted in increased reliability and ease of modifying and upgrading the system. PROFS employed top-down, structured software development techniques that produced inherently better documentation, and made code maintenance and modification relatively easy.

Efforts are underway to reconfigure the EDF to provide enhanced capabilities in the near future. An Ethernet local-area network is being installed in place of point-to-point DECnet communications links to improve communications throughput among the processors at the Boulder facility. A high-speed (70 megabits/sec) computer interconnect (VAXcluster) also will be implemented that will allow the sharing of mass storage resources among all VAX computers. The serial arrangement shown in Figure 1 will be replaced by a star configuration centered on the disk and tape storage devices. The new arrangement will eliminate the need for many data transfers that currently take place between processors and will provide additional redundancy that, in turn, will improve system reliability.

3. Application to Short-Range Forecasting

During the summers of 1982 and 1983, PROFS has conducted exercises aimed at evaluating the system's effectiveness in improving short-term, severe-storm forecasting. Data were acquired, products were generated, and the workstation was operated in real time. Operational forecasters used the system to generate site-specific forecasts and issue severe-weather warnings.

By touching the menu screen, the forecasters were able to display a large variety of products generated from the data listed in Section 2 on

Figure 2. Infrared GOES satellite image overlaid with height contours of the 500-mb pressure surface.

all four geographical scales. Figure 2 shows an example of an hourly National-scale product. In the figure, an infrared satellite image is remapped to polar stereographic projection and overlaid with a 500-mb pressure analysis. Figure 3 illustrates the PROFS mesonet station plot available every five minutes on the Local scale.

Figure 3. Local-scale PROFS mesonet station plot overlaid on Colorado county map background. The numbers for temperature (top left) and dew point (bottom left) are given for each station. Arrows show wind direction and barbs indicate wind speed (full barb corresponds to 10 knots, half barb to 5 knots). Wind gust values in excess of 10 knots are also shown at the arrowheads.

The Local scale was the area of forecast responsibility for the exercises. The power and flexibility of the workstation is demonstrated by Figure 4. Streamline analyses and Limon radar reflectivities are superimposed on the Local-scale mesonet station plot in the figure. Hourly plots of the WPL profiler-derived winds are given in Figure 5.

Short-range forecasting of severe weather has been recognized to be a difficult problem. Statistical analyses of the 1983 data set revealed a significant improvement in skill scores for issuing severe-thunderstorm warnings when compared to those issued using currently available operational equipment (McCoy, 1984). No comparable improvement in tornado warning skill was found. However, the results indicate strongly that the advanced technology and integrated data sets employed by the PROFS system will help to produce improved site-specific severe-weather forecasts as more experience is gained with the system.

Figure 4. Streamline analysis of the mesonet wind field and Limon radar reflectivities overlaid on mesonet station plot.

Figure 5. Hourly wind profiles between 3 and 15 km heights at Fleming, Colorado.

4. Application to Other Areas

The modular PROFS approach has allowed the application of PROFS-developed techniques to other, non-severe-storm related forecasting problems. During the past 12 months, five different system realizations have been developed. For example, PROFS has configured a system to generate improved upper-air wind analyses and forecasts for commercial aviation under NASA sponsorship. The successful test of the system

demonstrated the applicability of the PROFS methodology for much larger geographical areas covering the entire continental U. S.

We feel that the PROFS approach could have valuable applications for the ocean environment. Currently, PROFS is assisting the NOAA National Ocean Service, Office of Oceanography and Marine Services to size the system needed for the proposed Ocean Service Centers (OSC). The objective of the OSC project is to provide improved products and services to the marine community by bringing together and enhancing existing NOAA resources. PROFS is analyzing the needs for the major Ocean Service Centers and associated smaller centers. Our study has revealed significant commonalities between OSC's requirements and those of PROFS. A significant portion of the data in question is meteorological and is either the same as, or similar to that already handled by PROFS. Even ocean-specific data such as surface currents or XBT readings are quite analogous to data in the PROFS data base. For a given area, oceanographic data tend to be less frequent and of lower volume than comparable meteorological data. This indicates that OSC should not require significantly different computer power than that employed by PROFS. The similarities extend to data communications, data acquisition, and product generation. Some of the workstation functions probably need to be changed, but most of the changes should be rather minor. For example, a simple color table change makes it possible to display infrared-satellite-derived ocean surface temperatures instead of cloud-top temperatures.

5. Conclusions

PROFS has demonstrated that by using advanced digital technology and display devices, it is possible to develop a system for improved weather forecasting. Essential features of the PROFS effort were the integration of practically all available conventional and advanced meteorological data, rapid data updates, modular system implementation, extensive use of top-down, structured software techniques, and the development of a highly interactive user-friendly workstation. The initial application of the PROFS system was for severe-weather phenomena. However, the PROFS techniques are applicable for other types of problems including the ocean environment.

6. References

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